

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The Overeducated Employed in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022

They grew on average by 6.39%

Istat calculates the value of over-educated employees. The variable is defined as the percentage of employed people who have a higher educational qualification than the one best possessed to carry out that profession out of the total number of employed people. This variable is analysed for the 20 Italian regions from 2018 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of over-educated employees in 2022. Umbria is in first place in terms of value of over-educated employees in 2022 with a value of 33.1 units, followed by the Marche with a value of 30.8 units, and by Molise with a value of 30.3 units. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with a value of 27.4 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 27.2 units and Veneto with a value of 27 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a value of 23 units, followed by Lombardy with a value of 22.5 units, and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 21.1 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in over-educated employed between 2018 and 2022. Liguria is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in over-educated employed between 2018 and 2022 with a value of 15.48% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.2 units up to 29.1 units or equal to a variation of 3.9 units. Molise is in second place with a variation equal to 15.21% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.3 units up to a value of 30.3 units equal to an amount of 4 units. Sicily is in third place with a value equal to 14.04% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.8 units up to a value of 26 units corresponding to a value of 3.2 units.

In the middle of the table are Lazio with a value of 6.88% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 27.6 units up to a value of 29.5 units equal to 1.9 units. Umbria follows with a value of 6.77% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 31 units up to a value of 33.1 units equal to a value of 2.1 units. Below is Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 5.5% equal to a growth from 20.00 units up to a value of 21.1 units equal to an amount of 1.1 units.

In the last places are Calabria with a value of -0.73% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 27.4 units up to a value of 27.2 units equal to -0.2 units. Emilia-Romagna follows with a variation of -1.52% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.4 units up to 26 units equal to -0.4 units. Abruzzo closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 31.6 units up to a value of 30.2 units corresponding to a value of -1.4 units equal to a variation of -4.43%.

The over-educated employed in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. The over-educated employed in Northern Italy grew from an amount of 23.4 units up to a value of 24.6 units equal to a value of 1.2 units equal at a value of 5.13%. Over-educated employees in the North-West grew between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 22.3 units up to a value of 23.4 units corresponding to a

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

variation of 1.1 units equal to an amount of 4.93% . Over-educated employees in the North-East grew from an amount of 24.8 units up to a value of 26.2 units corresponding to a value of 1.4 units equal to a value of 5.65%. The over-educated employees in the Center grew from an amount of 27.2 units up to a value of 29.2 units corresponding to a variation of 2 units equal to an amount of 7.35%. Over-educated employees in the South grew between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 24.9 units up to 26.1 units equal to an amount of 1.2 units equal to 4.82%. Over-educated employees in Southern Italy grew from an amount of 25.8 units up to a value of 26.2 units equal to an amount of 0.4 units equal to a value of 1.55%. The over-educated employees in the Islands grew from a value of 22.9 units up to a value of 26 units equal to an amount of 3.1 units corresponding to a value of 13.54%.

We can note during Covid 19 the value of over-educated employees grew significantly especially in the North with +4.18%, in the North-West equal to +5.36%, Northeast with +2.31%, Center with +4.38% and in the Islands +1.64%. However, the value of over-educated employees decreased in the South with -0.78% and the South with -1.92%. Covid 19 has therefore tended to increase the value of over-educated employees with peaks in some regions, namely: Liguria with +7.11, Trentino Alto Adige with +10.53%, Friuli Venezia Giulia with +7.09%, Marche with + 10.41%, Molise with +8.28%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient highlights the presence of two clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Lazio, Molise, Abruzzo, Marche, Umbria, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Calabria, Emilia Romagna;
- Cluster 2: Sardinia, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Puglia, Sicily, Campania, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Liguria, Tuscany.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters we can note the dominance of cluster 1 compared to the value of cluster 2 or $C1 > C2$. We can note that both Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 have a heterogeneous composition from both an economic and geographical point of view. Therefore, it is not possible to find a contrast and re-proposal of the North-South divide within the clusters.

Conclusions. The value of over-educated employees grew from an amount of 25.42% up to a value of 27.05% or a growth of 6.39% on average in the Italian regions. The cluster analysis shows a very heterogeneous condition, which does not allow us to reproduce a contrast between Centre-North and South. Finally, Covid 19 has had an impact on the growth of the value of over-educated workers with the exception of the macro-regions of Southern Italy and South where the corresponding value decreased significantly. Around 27% of workers are therefore overeducated on average. As a result, they are also underpaid for their degrees. It follows that there is a salary issue that is not capable of effectively remunerating human capital based on training courses. A condition that leads to professional disqualification especially for graduates, masters and doctorates, in relation to which economic policy seems to be immobile. In fact, the idea has spread among the ruling class that workers are all without will and characterized by idleness and starvation. Therefore, they must not be helped in their income, career and work paths. The lack of adequate economic labour policies aimed at recognizing the value of qualifications and professional paths ends up disqualifying a significant part of human capital and justifying the refusal of NEETs, women and the unemployed to enter the world of work. The macro-economic consequence consists in the reduction of productivity and therefore in the impossibility for the Italian economy to be competitive and innovative, determining

the Italian economy's exit from the top ten countries both in terms of per capita income and GDP in absolute value.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Leogrande, D., & Anobile, F. (2023). Beds in Health Facilities in the Italian Regions: A Socio-Economic Approach. Available at SSRN 4577029.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, D. (2023). The Socio-Economic Determinants of the Number of Physicians in Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4560149.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of Unemployment in the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4502940.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Patent Applications in the Context of the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4514191.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Government Expenditure on Education in the ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4438106.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Determinants of Emissions in the Context of ESG Models at World Level.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4388957.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Patent Applications in the Context of the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4514191.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Fight Against Corruption at Global Level. A Metric Approach. A Metric Approach (December 30, 2022).

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis. A Data-Driven Analysis (December 25, 2022).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). k-Means Clusterization and Machine Learning Prediction of European Most Cited Scientific Publications. Available at SSRN 4195846

■ 2018 ■ 2019 ■ 2020 ■ 2021 ■ 2022

